

AN APPROACH TO q -SERIES

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Abstract

In this paper we prove a new q -series transformation using a very simple method.

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1. Introduction

From the theorems of L. Euler [6] and C. F. Gauss [8] to the works by E. Heine [11], S. Ramanujan [2,3], L. J. Rogers [13], W. N. Bailey [4], G. E. Andrews [1], G. Gasper and M. Rahman [7], and many others, there is a plethora of literature on q -series.

However, there are few tools available to prove these theorems. Functional equations, partial fractions, combinatorial reasoning and the powerful “Bailey’s lemma” introduced by W. N. Bailey [4] are among the techniques used by mathematicians.

“What is a q -series,” an eloquent paper written by B. C. Berndt [5], describes some of the main results and characters in the history of this subject.

No special knowledge about q -series is necessary to understand the development of this paper. Using a potentially new method, we derive a strange q -series transformation, from which several results follow. We employ the traditional notation in this field

$$(a; q)_n = (1 - a)(1 - aq) \dots (1 - aq^{n-1}), \quad n \in \mathbf{Z}^+,$$

$$(a; q)_0 = 1,$$

$$(a; q)_\infty = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - aq^m).$$

2. The Main Result

This paper is devoted to proving the general transformation which we state in the following proposition.

Proposition 1. Let $a_m(q)$ and $b_m(q)$, $m \in \mathbf{Z}^+$, be rational functions of q where $|q| < 1$ and $|z| < 1$. If

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q)y^m = (yq^2; q^2)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)y^m, \tag{1}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(-z, q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(-z; q)_m + 2z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(z^2, q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q)q^m(z^2; q^2)_m \\ = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z, q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(z; q)_m. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

3. A Pair of Lemmas

Before proving Proposition 1 we establish several lemmas.

Lemma 2. Let $|q| < 1$ and $|z| < 1$. Then

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m q^{\frac{m^2+m}{2}}}{(q; q)_m (1 - zq^m)} = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}}. \tag{3}$$

Proof. We need only to rewrite the last expression as

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m q^{\frac{m^2+m}{2}}}{(q; q)_m (1 - zq^m)} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (q^{m+1}; q)_{\infty} z^m = (q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^m}{(q; q)_m} = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}}.$$

To do so, we use two results by Euler [6]

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^m}{(q; q)_m} = \frac{1}{(z; q)_{\infty}}$$

and

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^m q^{\frac{m^2-m}{2}}}{(q; q)_m} = (z; q)_{\infty}.$$

□

Lemma 3. *Let $|q| < 1$ and $|z| < 1$. Then*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-zq^n} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} q^{\frac{(n-i)^2+n-i}{2}}}{(q; q)_{n-i}} b_i(q) \right) = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(z; q)_n, \quad (4)$$

Proof. The infinite double series

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q) \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m q^{\frac{m^2+m}{2}}}{(q; q)_m (1-zq^{m+n})} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q) \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(zq^n; q)_{\infty}}$$

can be rewritten in the more appropriate form

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-zq^n} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n b_i(q) \frac{(-1)^{n-i} q^{\frac{(n-i)^2+(n-i)}{2}}}{(q; q)_{n-i}} \right) = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(z; q)_n.$$

□

4. An Additional Lemma and an Important Result

In the following section we establish an additional lemma and highlight an important result used in its proof.

Lemma 4. *Let $|q| < 1$ and $|z| < 1$. Then*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^n}{1-z^2q^{2n}} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} a_i(q) q^{(n-i)^2}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-i}} \right) = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(z^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(q) q^n (z^2; q^2)_n. \quad (5)$$

Proof. In this case, we begin with the double series

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(q) q^n \left(\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^m q^{m^2+m}}{(q^2; q^2)_m (1-z^2q^{2m+2n})} \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(q) q^n \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(z^2q^{2n}; q^2)_{\infty}},$$

We can then rewrite the last identity as we did in (4). □

Now we can multiply (8) by $(yq; q^2)_{\infty}$ to find

$$(yq; q^2)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q) y^m = (yq; q)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q) y^m.$$

Equating coefficients of y^n on both sides, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} a_i(q) q^{(n-i)^2}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-i}} = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} b_i(q) q^{\frac{(n-i)^2+(n-i)}{2}}}{(q; q)_{n-i}}. \tag{6}$$

Therefore we can substitute the right side of (6) into the left-hand side of (4) to obtain the important result mentioned earlier

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-zq^n} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} q^{\frac{(n-i)^2+(n-i)}{2}}}{(q; q)_{n-i}} b_i(q) \right) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-zq^n} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} a_i(q) q^{(n-i)^2}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-i}} \right) \\ &= \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(z; q)_n. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

5. Proof of the Main Identity

We first restate the main identity of the paper before providing a proof.

Proposition 1. *Let $a_m(q)$ and $b_m(q)$, $m \in \mathbf{Z}^+$, be rational functions of q where $|q| < 1$ and $|z| < 1$. If*

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q) y^m = (yq^2; q^2)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q) y^m, \tag{8}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(-z, q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(-z; q)_m + 2z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(z^2, q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q) q^m (z^2; q^2)_m \\ = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z, q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(z; q)_m. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Proof. We only need to replace z with $-z$ in (7), multiply (5) by $2z$, and then add both identities:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(z; q)_n + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(-z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(-z; q)_n + z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(z^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(q) q^n (z^2; q^2)_n \\ = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-zq^n} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-1)^{n-i} a_i(q) q^{(n-i)^2}}{(q^2; q^2)_{n-i}} \right) = \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n(q)(z; q)_n. \end{aligned}$$

□

6. Applications and Examples

Application 5: Mock theta functions. We take the product

$$(-yq^2; q^2)_\infty (yq^2; q^2)_\infty = (y^2q^4; q^4)_\infty,$$

where

$$(-yq^2; q^2)_\infty = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{q^{n^2+n}y^n}{(q^2; q^2)_n} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty b_n(q)y^n$$

and

$$(y^2q^4; q^4)_\infty = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^n q^{2(n^2+n)} y^{2n}}{(q^4; q^4)_n} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty a_n(q)y^n.$$

If we then insert $a_n(q)$ and $b_n(q)$ from above into (9), we find

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(-z; q)_\infty} \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{q^{n^2+n}(-z; q)_n}{(q^2; q^2)_n} + 2z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}{(z^2; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^m q^{2(m^2+m)} q^{2m} (z^2; q^2)_{2m}}{(q^4; q^4)_m} \\ = \frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(z; q)_\infty} \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{q^{n^2+n} (z; q)_n}{(q^2; q^2)_n}. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

We now need the classical result of Rogers [13]

$$\frac{1}{(q^2; q^5)_\infty (q^3; q^5)_\infty} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{q^{n^2+n}}{(q; q)_n}.$$

Thus, in (10) by replacing z with q , we finally obtain

$$\frac{(q; q^5)_\infty (q^4; q^5)_\infty (q^5; q^5)_\infty}{(-q; q)_\infty} + \frac{2}{q} \sum_{n=0}^\infty (-1)^n q^{2(n+1)^2} (q^2; q^4)_n = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{q^{n^2+n}}{(-q; q)_n}. \tag{11}$$

This is a famous identity first proved by G. N. Watson [14] for the fifth order mock theta functions.

Application 6: A New Result from a Classic Identity. In this case we choose

$$\sum_{m=0}^\infty a_m(q)y^m = (-yq; q^2)_\infty = \sum_{m=0}^\infty \frac{q^{m^2}}{(q^2; q^2)_m}$$

and

$$\sum_{m=0}^\infty b_m(q)y^m = \frac{(-yq; q^2)_\infty}{(yq^2; q^2)_\infty} = \sum_{m=0}^\infty y^m q^{2m} \frac{(-q^{-1}; q^2)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m}.$$

Inserting these results into (9) we find

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q, q)_\infty}{(-z; q)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty q^{2m} \frac{(-q^{-1}; q^2)_m (-z; q)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m} + 2z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}{(z^2; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty \frac{q^{m^2+m} (z^2; q^2)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m} \\ = \frac{(q, q)_\infty}{(z; q)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty q^{2m} \frac{(-q^{-1}; q^2)_m (z; q)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m}. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In the last identity V. A. Lebesgue’s [12] classic result appears:

$$\sum_{m=0}^\infty \frac{q^{m^2+m} (z^2; q^2)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m} = (z^2 q^2; q^4)_\infty (-q^2; q^2)_\infty.$$

Therefore we can rewrite (12) as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(q, q)_\infty}{(-z; q)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty q^{2m} \frac{(-q^{-1}; q^2)_m (-z; q)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m} + 2z \frac{(q^4; q^4)_\infty}{(z^2; q^4)_\infty} \\ = \frac{(q, q)_\infty}{(z; q)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty q^{2m} \frac{(-q^{-1}; q^2)_m (z; q)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m}, \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

which appears to be a new result.

Application 7: An Interesting Identity. In this example, we take

$$\sum_{m=0}^\infty a_m(q) y^m = (yq^2; q^2)_\infty = \sum_{m=0}^\infty (-1)^m \frac{q^{m^2+m}}{(q^2; q^2)_m},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_0 &= 1, \\ b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

If we use these results in (9), we find

$$\frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(-z; q)_\infty} + 2z \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}{(z^2; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^\infty (-1)^m \frac{q^{m^2+2m} (z^2; q^2)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m} = \frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(z; q)_\infty}. \tag{14}$$

Using the previous identity, we can obtain the following interesting result. If

$$\frac{1}{(q; q^2)_\infty} = \sum_{m=0}^\infty c_m q^m$$

then

$$\sum_{m=1}^\infty c_{2m-1} q^m = (q^2, q^2)_\infty \sum_{m=0}^\infty (-1)^m \frac{q^{(m+1)^2} (q; q^2)_m}{(q^2; q^2)_m}. \tag{15}$$

Another possibility is using the second Göllnitz-Gordon [9,10] identity

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{n^2+2n}(-q; q^2)_n}{(q^2, q^2)_n} = \frac{1}{(q^3; q^8)_{\infty}(q^4; q^8)_{\infty}(q^5; q^8)_{\infty}}$$

in (14) where $q \rightarrow -q$ and $z = i\sqrt{q}$. From this we obtain

$$\frac{(iq^{\frac{1}{2}}; q^2)_{\infty}(-iq^{\frac{3}{2}}; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}(-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} + \frac{2i\sqrt{q}}{(q^3; q^8)_{\infty}(q^4; q^8)_{\infty}(q^5; q^8)_{\infty}} = \frac{(-iq^{\frac{1}{2}}; q^2)_{\infty}(iq^{\frac{3}{2}}; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}(-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}.$$

The following identity is equivalent. If

$$(-q; q^2)_{\infty} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m q^m,$$

then

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} (-1)^m a_{2m+1} q^m = \frac{(q^1; q^8)_{\infty}(q^7; q^8)_{\infty}(-q^4; q^4)_{\infty}}{(q^2; q^4)_{\infty}}.$$

7. An Alternative Proof of the Main Identity

G. E. Andrews graciously provided the author with the following alternative proof of identity (9):

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(-z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(-z; q)_m + \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(z; q)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q)(z; q)_m = \\ & = (q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q) \left(\frac{-1}{(-zq^m; q)_{\infty}} + \frac{1}{(zq^m; q)_{\infty}} \right) \\ & = (q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^j q^{mj} ((-1)^{j+1} + 1)}{(q; q)_j} \\ & = 2(q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2j+1}}{(q; q)_{2j+1}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} b_m(q) q^{m(2j+1)} \\ & = 2(q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2j+1}}{(q; q)_{2j+1}} \frac{1}{(q^{2j+3}; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q) q^{m(2j+1)} \\ & = 2 \frac{(q; q)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2j+1}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} a_m(q) q^{m(2j+1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2(q^2; q^2)_\infty \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} zq^m a_m(q) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2j} q^{2jm}}{(q^2; q^2)_j} \\
 &= 2(q^2; q^2)_\infty \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{zq^m a_m(q)}{(z^2 q^{2m}; q^2)_\infty} = 2 \frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}{(z^2; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} zq^m a_m(q) (z^2; q^2)_m.
 \end{aligned}$$

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